

DIAGNOSIS AND TREATMENT OF OBSTRUCTIVE JAUNDICE SYNDROME

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Annotation

In this work, we analyzed the results of diagnostics and treatment of 146 patients with benign mechanical jaundice syndrome treated at the Samarkand Central Emerging Medical Center from 2023 to 2025. Depending on the bilirubin level as an integral indicator, the patients were divided into 3 groups. In the comprehensive diagnostics of the functional state of the liver, all 132 patients used ultrasound, MCCT, MRI, as well as gas-liquid chromatography and spectrometry. The main attention was paid to the use of minimally invasive methods of biliary system decompression in the treatment of patients with mechanical jaundice syndrome. Despite the elimination of biliary hypertension in patients of group 3, aggravation of cytolysis and endotoxiosis syndrome was noted in the postoperative period. Of this group, 2 patients with increasing hepatocerebral insufficiency died. The presented data show the need for further developments in diagnostics and treatment of patients with severe mechanical jaundice syndrome.

Key words: mechanical jaundice syndrome, bilirubin level, minimally invasive interventions, liver failure.

Introduction

Technology in biliary surgery has not yet come to a full understanding of the pathogenesis and pathological conditions in the body due to impaired bile outflow through the bile ducts. The problem of effective treatment of patients with mechanical jaundice remains relevant to this day, despite the positive results in biliary surgery. The main cause of mortality in patients with mechanical jaundice of benign genesis is the progression of liver failure after surgical intervention on the bile ducts. Of the many methods for preventing the progression of liver failure, great importance is currently attached to external drainage of the bile ducts. Surgical interventions undertaken against the background of mechanical jaundice cannot be performed radically in most patients and are accompanied by the development of complications in 47-68% of cases. Despite modern achievements in the fight against mechanical jaundice, the mortality rate of liver failure, irreversible dysfunction of hepatocytes, remains high 5.6-6.3%. A two-stage

tactic has become widespread in the treatment of such patients: at the first stage, decompression of the bile ducts is performed, at the second - palliative or radical surgical interventions. Such tactics allow to reduce the frequency of postoperative complications by 17.0%, and mortality to 2.8%.

Objective of the study: to study the functional state of the liver in patients with mechanical jaundice syndrome of non-tumor genesis based on anamnesis, instrumental and clinical laboratory data.

Materials and methods of research

During the period from 2023 to 2025, 146 patients with choledocholithiasis complicated by mechanical jaundice syndrome were treated at the Samarkand Center for Emergency Medical Care. Depending on the level of bilirubinemia, as an integral indicator, patients were divided into three groups: Group 1 - 48 (32.8%) patients whose bilirubin level did not exceed $100 \mu\text{mol} / \text{l}$ (an average of $88.6 \mu\text{mol} / \text{l}$) and with a duration of jaundice of no more than 5 days. The second group - 46 (31.5%) patients with a bilirubin level within $100\text{-}200 \mu\text{mol} / \text{l}$ (on average $188.1 \mu\text{mol} / \text{l}$), with mechanical jaundice lasting no more than 10 days. The third group included 50 (34.2%) patients whose bilirubin level and jaundice duration exceeded $200 \mu\text{mol} / \text{l}$ and *12 days*, respectively. The average blood bilirubin level in the 3-g group was $256 \mu\text{mol} / \text{l}$.

In the complex diagnostics of the functional state of the liver in all 146 patients, ultrasound, gas-liquid chromatography, and spectrophotometry were used. Patients in the study groups were assessed for transaminase activity, the dynamics of the concentrations of medium molecules, the level of bile phosphatase, cholesterol and bilirubin.

The severity of mechanical jaundice was established on the basis of clinical and laboratory data and the results of instrumental studies: ultrasound examination of the abdominal cavity; plain radiography of the chest and abdominal organs; multispiral computed tomography of the abdominal organs with contrast; magnetic resonance cholangiopancreatography; esophagogastroduodenoscopy. Cholangioscopy, endoscopic retrograde cholangiopancreatography, percutaneous transhepatic cholangiography, videolaparoscopy, duodenoscopy, fistulography, radiocontrast examination of the digestive organs systems.

In 146 patients, various types of biliary drainage were used: percutaneous transhepatic cholangiostomy - 45; endoscopic - 45; papillosphincterotomy with nasobiliary drainage - 58; nasobiliary drainage - 18, percutaneous transhepatic external-internal drainage - in 17; endoscopic papillosphincterotomy - in 37; stenting - in 9. All patients underwent bacteriological examination of bile contents for aerobic and anaerobic flora with determination of sensitivity to antibiotics. When performing EEG, the patient wears a cap with electrodes, signals from the brain are transmitted through the electrodes to a device - an encephalograph.

The studies were conducted on EEG (Neurotravel SMART and GEM 100).

Electroencephalography was performed on patients to verify the degree of hepatocerebral insufficiency. EEG indications were bilirubin > 300 $\mu\text{mol/l}$, psychomotor agitation, sleep disorders, there were 8 such patients.

Static analysis

Statistical data were analyzed using t-test, Pearson χ^2 test and Fisher's exact test. The data were analyzed using SPSS for Windows version 17.0 (SPSS 1 ps., USA) $p < 0.05$ is considered significant.

Research results and their discussion

At the time of admission, patients in group 1 with jaundice lasting up to 5 *days* , according to clinical and laboratory data, had signs of mild or moderate hepatopathy: blood bilirubin level averaging 88.6 $\mu\text{mol/l}$, moderate hyperfermentemia - AST 0.6-0.8 $\mu\text{mol/hL}$, ALT - 0.6-0.8 $\mu\text{mol/hL}$, LDH - 9.4-9.8 $\mu\text{mol/hL}$, moderate hypoproteinemia (total protein 56-60 g/l). Other biochemical parameters are normal. The patients did not show signs of hepatocerebral insufficiency, pathological changes in the encephalograms were not detected. The postoperative period in patients of group 1 was uneventful. The general condition on days 3-4 was assessed as relatively satisfactory. The skin acquired a natural color on days 4-5 after eliminating the obstruction to the bile flow, biochemical parameters approached values close to normal on *days 5-6* of the postoperative period. The use of *minimally* invasive The use of atregrade treatment methods allowed to perform decompression of biliary hypertension in 100% of cases . In patients of the 2nd group, the bilirubin level at the time of admission averaged 188 $\mu\text{mol/l}$, AST and ALT indicators were 2.6-3.7 $\mu\text{mol/hL}$ and 1.9-2.9 $\mu\text{mol/hL}$, respectively, LDH - 17.6-20.6 $\mu\text{mol/hL}$, moderate hypoproteinemia was noted (total protein 54-59 g / l), compared with the first group ($p < 0.05$). Along with this, patients of the 2nd group had signs of endotoxicosis: blood toxicity according to the paramecium test averaged 16.7 min., the level of medium-sized molecules was 0.56-0.69 U. All patients in group 2 had no obvious clinical signs of hepatocerebral insufficiency at the time of admission, however, after the writing test and the counting back test, signs of encephalopathy *were detected in 8 (5.5%) patients*. The EEG performed in these patients indicated the presence of grade 1 hepatocerebral insufficiency - uneven alpha rhythm, mild but stable beta and delta waves. The use of retrograde techniques for mechanical jaundice syndrome was effective in 89.6% of cases, in 10.4% of cases it was necessary to perform traditional cholecystolithotomy due to large common bile duct stones. In 14.2% of cases, combined drainage of the bile ducts was used. After the surgical intervention, for 2-4 days postoperative period in 6 patients of group 2 against the background of an increase in bilirubin of more than 300 $\mu\text{mol/l}$, worsening endotoxicosis (blood toxicity according to the paramecium test up to 13 min., the level of medium molecules was 0.79-0.86 U.S.) ($r = 0.8$; $p < 0.001$; $n=8$) and emotional, mental disorders were noted, manifested by rapid mood swings, depression or

euphoria, sleep inversion, headache. These changes are characteristic of hepatocerebral insufficiency of 1-2 degrees, which was confirmed by characteristic changes in the EEG.

At the time of admission, patients in group 3 with jaundice lasting more than 12 days, according to clinical and laboratory data, had signs of hepatopathy (severe) degree ($p = 0.004$): the level of bilirubin in the blood was on average $256 \mu\text{mol/l}$, severe hyperenzymemia: AST - $3.6-3.8 \mu\text{mol/hL}$, ALT - $3.16-4.0 \mu\text{mol/hL}$, LDH - $29.7-30.1 \mu\text{mol/hL}$, moderate hypoproteinemia (total protein $54-58 \text{ g/l}$) ($p=0.08$). The cholesterol level averaged 7.9 mmol/l , urea - 14.3 mmol/l , alkaline phosphatase - $4.8 \mu\text{mol/l}$, blood toxicity according to the paramecium test averaged 10.8 min , the level of medium-sized molecules was $0.8-0.9 \text{ U}$. Patients of group 3 in comparison with those of groups 1 and 2 had the most severe somatic status: prolonged mechanical jaundice, cholangitis, aggravated by the presence of concomitant pathology. In the 3rd group, the use of retrograde methods of mechanical jaundice syndrome was effective in 65.6% of cases, in 20.8% of cases it was necessary to perform traditional choledocholithotomy, due to large stones of the common bile duct and the Merisi symptom ($p=0.001$). In 13.6% of cases, combined drainage of the bile ducts was performed using the "Rendezvous" method due to the impossibility of adequate drainage of the bile ducts in a retrograde manner.

Despite the elimination of biliary hypertension, these patients experienced worsening of cytotoxicity syndrome and endotoxemia in the immediate postoperative period. ALT levels and the concentration of medium molecules exceeded the initial levels before surgery, prolonged hyperbilirubinemia was observed - 38 (26.0%) patients in the study group with signs of increasing liver failure, symptoms of hepatocerebral failure - 2 (5.3%) died.

Conclusions

1. The use of retrograde interventions made it possible to increase the effectiveness of treatment of mechanical jaundice of benign origin from 75.5% to 89.6% ($p<0.001$).
2. Rapid decompression of the bile ducts leads to the development of reperfusion syndrome, which is one of the causes of liver failure.
4. The stages of bile duct decompression and reduction of the level of intoxication in patients with liver failure against the background of mechanical jaundice require further development.

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